

TOTAL WAR OF THE PAST IN INDONESIA, CASE STUDY: JAVA / DIPONEGORO WAR

Munif Prasojo¹, Tati Herlia¹, I Wayan Midhio², Deni Dadang², Rizerius Eko Sancoko², Lukman Yudho Prakoso²

¹(Research and Development Agency / Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia, Indonesia)

²(Faculty of Defense Strategy / Indonesian Defense University, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT:- Indonesia has experienced a dark period of being colonized by the Dutch for 3.5 centuries. During this colonial period, there was much resistance by the Indonesian people from various regions. One of the Indonesian people's resistance to Dutch colonial rule was the Diponegoro War (Sejarah Strategi "Benteng Stelsel" Belanda Di Perang Diponegoro | Merdeka.Com, n.d.-a)

The Diponegoro War, also known as the Java War (English: The Java War, Dutch: De Java Oorlog), was a major war and lasted for five years (1825-1830) on the island of Java, Dutch East Indies (now Indonesia). This war was one of the biggest battles the Dutch had ever experienced during their archipelago occupation of the Dutch troops under the leadership of General Hendrik Merkus de Kock, who tried to reduce the resistance of the Javanese population under the supervision of Prince Diponegoro. As a result of this war, the Javanese population who died reached 200,000 people, while the death toll on the Dutch side was 8,000 Dutch soldiers and 7000 native soldiers. The end of the war confirmed Dutch control of Java Island.

Contrary to the war that was led by Raden Ronggo some 15 years earlier, the Javanese troops also placed the Chinese community in Java as the target of attack. However, although Pangeran Diponegoro strictly prohibited his troops from allying with the Chinese community, some Javanese soldiers on the north coast (around Rembang and Lasem) received assistance from local Chinese residents, primarily Muslims.

KEYWORDS – Javanese War, Diponegoro, Stelsel, Yogyakarta, Total War

I. INTRODUCTION

1. Preliminary

The Diponegoro War, or Java War, was a major war and lasted for five years from 1825-1830. This war was motivated by the hatred of the Javanese people against the Dutch for the oppression in Java. As the name implies, this war was led by Pangeran Diponegoro, who was the Prince of the Yogyakarta Sultanate.

In its history, since the arrival of Marshal Herman Willem Daendels in Batavia, Dutch colonial influence has become increasingly apparent on the island of Java, especially the Yogyakarta Palace. Daendels changed the etiquette and ceremony procedures that caused hatred on the part of the Javanese Palace. He forced the Yogyakarta Palace to access various natural and human resources by mobilizing his military power.

After Sri Sultan Hamengkubuwono IV died, Yogyakarta Resident Jonkheer Anthonie Hendrik Smislaert interfered a lot in matters of palace power. Where many unilateral policies were smoothed by him, at that time, Pangeran Diponegoro, who became the regent of the King, could not stand the presence of the Dutch at the Yogyakarta Palace. Finally, he chose to return to his residence in Tegalrejo.

a. The reign of Daendles and Raffles

The feud between the Javanese court and the Dutch began with Marshal Herman Willem Daendels in Batavia on January 5, 1808. Although he was only assigned to prepare Java as a defense

base for France against England (at that time, the Dutch were controlled by France), Daendels also changed the etiquette and order. The ceremony caused hatred on the part of the Javanese court. He forced the Yogyakarta Palace to give him access to various natural and human resources by mobilizing his military force, building a route between Anyer and Panarukan until finally, the teak trade incident occurred in the foreign area (Java region east of Yogyakarta), which led to the Raden Ronggo rebellion. After the Raden Ronggo rebellion (1810) failure, Daendels forced Sultan Hamengkubuwana II to pay war losses and carried out various other insults, which led to clashes between the royal families (1811). However, in the same year, British troops landed on Java and defeated the Dutch forces.

Although the British, led by Thomas Stamford Bingley Raffles, gave support to Sultan Hamengkubuwana II, British troops finally attacked the Yogyakarta Palace (19-20 June 1812), which caused Sultan Hamengkubuwana II to abdicate dishonorably and was replaced by his eldest son, Sultan Hamengkubuwana III. This event is known as Geger Sepahi. Britain ruled until 1815 and returned Java to the Dutch according to the contents of the Vienna Agreement (1814) under the Dutch Governor-General van der Capellen. During British rule, Hamengkubuwana III died and was replaced by his son, Prince Diponegoro's half-brother, namely Hamengkubuwana IV, who was ten years old (1814), while Paku Alam I became duke of Puro Kadipaten Pakualaman as well as regent, while Patih Danuredjo III acted as regent

b. HB V Appointment and the Smissaert Government

On December 6, 1822, Hamengkubuwana IV died at the age of 19. Ratu Ageng (empress of Hamengkubuwana II) and Gusti Kangjeng Ratu Kencono (empress of Hamengkubuwana IV) strongly appealed to the Dutch government to confirm Hamengkubuwana IV's 2-year-old son to become Hamengkubuwana V and no longer make Paku Alam as guardian. Pangeran Diponegoro was subsequently appointed guardian of his nephew along with Mangkubumi.

The new Resident of Yogyakarta to replace Nahuys, Jonkheer Anthonie Hendrik Smissaert, went too far by being involved in the appointment of the Sultan in June 1823. This appointment was to replace Sultan Hamengku Buwono III, who suddenly died. Smissaert sits on the throne while receiving the worship and devotion of international regents in five Garebeg ceremonies during his 31-month tenure as Resident. In the eyes of the Javanese, this was an insult to their dignity. (Peter Carey: 2014)

Pangeran Diponegoro still accepted the position of Wali Sultan along with Mangkubumi, Ratu Ageng, and Ratu Kencono (the mother of the toddler Sultan). However, the Prince's place was increasingly neglected. Smissaert ignored Pangeran Diponegoro's opinion on compensation for land leases that could lead to bankruptcy for the Sultanate.

Following Van der Graaf's observation in 1821 that saw local farmers suffering from the misuse of land leases by Dutch, British, French, and German citizens, van der Capellen issued a decree on May 6, 1823, that all land leased by Europeans and Chinese must be returned. To their owners as of January 31, 1824. However, landowners were obliged to provide compensation to European land tenants. The Yogyakarta Palace was threatened with bankruptcy because the land that was rented belonged to the palace. Prince Diponegoro was forced to borrow money from the Chinese chief in Yogyakarta at that time. Smissaert managed to trick the two sultan's guardians into passing the compensation requested by Nahuys for the plantation in Bedoyo, causing Diponegoro to cut ties with the palace. The severance of this relationship was mainly due to the actions of Ratu Ageng (the Prince's stepmother) and Patih Danurejo, who were pro-Dutch. On October 29, 1824, Pangeran Diponegoro held a meeting at his house in Tegalrejo to discuss the possibility of a rebellion in mid-August. Pangeran Diponegoro made up his mind to fight back by canceling the Puwasa tax so that the farmers in Tegalrejo could buy weapons and food.

c. Start of the War

In mid-May 1825, Smissaert decided to repair the small roads around Yogyakarta. However, the road construction that started from Yogyakarta to Magelang through Muntilan was diverted through the

eastern fence of Tegalrejo, and the Dutch installed road repair poles along with the ancestral graves of Pangeran Diponegoro.

It was this act of the Dutch that provoked the anger of Prince Diponegoro and the local people. Finally, Pangeran Diponegoro replaced the stakes with spears as a sign of a declaration of war against the Dutch.

Prince Diponegoro launched a strategy of war against the Dutch for five years. He used guerrilla tactics by carrying out cover-ups, blitzkriegs, and invisible sieges. Meanwhile, to fight and defeat Diponegoro's troops, the Dutch, led by General Hendrik De Kock, implemented the Fort Stelsel strategy, namely by establishing a fort in each controlled area and connected by roads so that communication and troop movements would move smoothly. In the end, Fort Stelsel's strategy succeeded in breaking up the opposing forces so that they were easier to defeat. Where, in 1829 Kyai Mojo as the spiritual leader of the rebellion was arrested, after which Prince Mangkubumi and his chief commander Alibasah Sentot Prawirodirjo surrendered to the Dutch (What is meant by Fort Stelsel How is it done ?, n.d.-a) (*Apa Yang Dimaksud Dengan Benteng Stelsel Bagaimana Pelaksanaannya?*, n.d.).

Finally, on March 28, 1830, General De Kock succeeded in pinning Diponegoro's troops in Magelang. There, Pangeran Diponegoro stated that he was willing to surrender on the condition that the remaining members of his army were released. Therefore, Pangeran Diponegoro was arrested and exiled to Manado and then transferred to Makassar until his death at Rotterdam Fort on January 8, 1855.

The Diponegoro War was one of the biggest battles the Dutch had ever experienced during their occupation of the archipelago. As a result of this war, the Javanese who died reached 200 thousand people, while the death toll on the Dutch side was 8,000 Dutch soldiers and 7,000 native soldiers. The end of the Diponegoro War confirmed Dutch control over Java Island.

This war arose due to policies that did not make sense from the Dutch Colonial, such as the taking of aristocratic lands by the Dutch East Indies government. There were also kings who felt that they were victims of sheepfights and the Mataram kingdom was divided into 4 parts, namely Surakarta, Yogyakarta, Pakualam, and Mangkunegaraan (War Against Dutch Colonial Colonialism - Smart Class, n.d.) (*Perang Melawan Penjajahan Kolonial Belanda - Kelas Pintar*, n.d.).

Also, the Dutch planned to build a railway line in the area sacred to Prince Diponegoro so that there was resistance. Pangeran Diponegoro used guerrilla war tactics where they did it secretly, quickly, focused, and effectively.

Finally, the Dutch used a trick by inviting Prince Diponegoro to negotiate to solve the problem in Magelang. However, Prince Diponegoro was caught and exiled to Manado and transferred to Makassar until he died in 1855.

The Diponegoro War, also known as the Java War, was a major war and lasted for five years from 1825-1830 on Java. This war was one of the biggest battles the Dutch had ever experienced during their occupation of the archipelago.

As a result, around 200 thousand Javanese warriors were killed, and in the Dutch stronghold, about 8000 Dutch soldiers were killed. As the name implies, this war was led by Prince Diponegoro, who was supported by the palace, the clergy, and the people of Yogyakarta. The feud between the Javanese Palace and the Dutch began when Marshal Herman Willem Daendels arrived in Batavia on January 5, 1808 (What Do You Know About the Diponegoro War? - Smart Class, n.d.) (*Apa Yang Kamu Ketahui Tentang Perang Diponegoro?* - Kelas Pintar, n.d.).

One of the causes of the Diponegoro War was the action of the Dutch, who installed a stake for the construction of a road that passed through the grave of Pangeran Diponegoro's ancestral land in Tegalrejo without permission. So Pangeran Diponegoro replaced the stake with a spear, which made the Dutch angry and thought that Pangeran Diponegoro had rebelled so that he intended to arrest him.

This, of course, was not accepted by the people, so they declared war on the Netherlands. In dealing with Dutch troops, Pangeran Diponegoro used guerrilla tactics by carrying out deception, lightning attacks, and invisible sieges. In dealing with Indonesian tactics, the Dutch forces, which De Kock led, used the Fort Stelsel tactic by establishing a fort in each area under their control connected by roads to move smoothly.

This fortress system kept Diponegoro's troops pinned so that in 1829 Kyai Mojo, who was the spiritual leader of the rebellion, was arrested. Following that, Prince Mangkubumi and his chief commander Alibasah Sentot Prawirodirjo surrendered to the Dutch. Finally, on March 28, 1830, General De Kock succeeded in pinning Diponegoro's troops in Magelang, and Pangeran Diponegoro offered on the condition that the remaining members of his army were released.

After surrendering, Prince Diponegoro was exiled to Manado and transferred back to Makassar until he died at Fort Rotterdam on January 8, 1855. The end of the Javanese War was the end of the Javanese aristocratic resistance, where after the war ended, the population of Yogyakarta shrank by half.

This Java war broke out and lasted for approximately five years, from 1825 to 1830. It was quite a war. Pangeran Diponegoro led about 100,000 troops. The Prince's opponent was crushed by General Hendrik Merkus de Kock, who had 50,000 troops. This great war claimed many lives. The Dutch had to lose about 15,000 soldiers, while on the side of Pangeran Diponegoro, the victims who died were around 20,000 people. Material losses were estimated at 20 million guilders (The Death of 15 Thousand Dutch Soldiers in the Java War, n.d.). (*Tewasnya 15 Ribu Serdadu Belanda Pada Perang Jawa*, n.d.).

The Diponegoro War raged in remote parts of Central Java and features of East Java. Prince Diponegoro received support from various aristocrats, community leaders, scholars, students, and even commoners. The scholars who supported and fought with him included Kiai Mojo, Haji Mustopo, Haji Badaruddin, and Alibasaha Sentot Prawirodirjo.

At the beginning of the war, namely in 1825 - 1826, Pangeran Diponegoro's troops won several victories. He managed to paralyze the power base of the colonial forces in Pacitan and Purwodadi, then mastered it. The success achieved by Pangeran Diponegoro was thanks to the militancy of Javanese fighters and the ingenuity of Prince Diponegoro and his troops in implementing a multi-method war strategy based on hit and run tactics - a war tactic that was used. Very sophisticated and modern. The Dutch recognized this tactic of war as a very sophisticated tactic of war and had never been put into practice.

Figure 1. The arrest of Pangeran Diponegoro by Lieutenant General Hendrik Merkus de Kock on 28 March 1830, by Raden Saleh. Photo: Wikipedia

To fight Prince Diponegoro, the Dutch implemented the strategy of stelsel fort. Every area or area controlled by the Dutch was built a defense fort, then from each of these fortresses, a connecting infrastructure was built between the forts through roads or bridges. The implementation ? nd)(*Apa Yang Dimaksud Dengan Benteng Stelsel Bagaimana Pelaksanaannya?*, n.d.).

To narrow the space for Prince Diponegoro to move, the Dutch built stelsel forts in many places in Java, including; Semarang, Ambarawa, Muntilan, Kulonprogo, Magelang, and in other areas. No less than 165 stelsel forts were built by the Dutch (History of the Dutch "Fort Stelsel" Strategy in the Diponegoro War | Merdeka.Com, n.d.-b)(*Sejarah Strategi "Benteng Stelsel" Belanda Di Perang Diponegoro | Merdeka.Com, n.d.-a*).

And this strategy succeeded in paralyzing the movement of Pangeran Diponegoro with his troops. So in 1829, many fighters surrendered, and Prince Diponegoro was arrested in the Magelang area in 1830 (What is the Stelsel Fort System? Definition of the Stelsel Fort System and Its Definition in the Glossary, n.d.)(*Apa Itu Sistem Benteng Stelsel? Pengertian Sistem Benteng Stelsel Dan Definisinya Dalam Glosarium, n.d.*).

d. Sabil war

For Diponegoro and his followers, this war was a jihad war against the Dutch and the apostate Javanese. As a devout Muslim, Diponegoro felt displeased with the slack religiosity at the Yogyakarta palace due to the influence of the Dutch entry and the pro-Dutch policies issued by the court. The Dutch infiltration in the castle had made the Yogyakarta Palace like a brothel. On the other hand, Smissaert wrote that Prince Diponegoro was increasingly drifting into fanaticism, and many members of the kingdom considered him conservative in religion.

Lieutenant Jean Nicolaas de Thierry described Prince Diponegoro wearing an Arabic-style dress and an entirely white turban in his report. The clothes were also worn by Diponegoro's troops and were considered more critical than traditional Javanese clothing even though the war had ended. The description of Paulus Daniel Portier, an Indo, stated that the Dutch prisoners of war were threatened with life if they refused to convert to Islam.

II. THE COURSE OF THE WAR

2. The course of the war

Figure 2. Map of New Mataram after the Diponegoro War in 1830

Figure 3. Diponegoro

Figure 4. Alibasah Sentot

Open battles with the deployment of infantry, cavalry, and artillery (which since the Napoleonic wars have been the mainstay weapons in frontal combat) were fierce on both sides. Front battles took place in dozens of cities and villages across Java. The fighting took place so fiercely that if Dutch troops could control an area during the day, by night, the site would have been recaptured by native troops; vice versa. Logistics routes were built from one region to another to support war needs. Dozens of gunpowder refineries were built in forests and at the bottom of ravines. The production of gunpowder and bullets continued while the war was raging. Coders and couriers scrambled to find and convey the information needed to strategize the war. Information regarding enemy strength, distance and time, terrain conditions, rainfall made headlines because actual tactics and strategies could only be developed through mastery of knowledge.

The major attacks of the indigenous people were always carried out in the rainy months; the senopathy was well aware of cooperating with nature as an invincible "weapon." When the rainy season arrives, the Dutch government will make efforts to a ceasefire and negotiate because the heavy tropical rain hampers the movement of their troops. Malaria, dysentery, and so on are "invisible enemies," weakening their morale and physical condition and even claiming the lives of their forces. When a ceasefire occurs, the Dutch will consolidate their troops and deploy their spies and provocateurs across the villages and cities, incited, divided, and even suppressed the family members of princes and leaders of the people's struggle who were fighting under the command of Pangeran Diponegoro. However, these native fighters were not afraid and continued to fight against the Dutch.

Figure 5. Search for Diponegoro in Magelang.

In 1827, the Dutch attacked Diponegoro using a fort system so that the Diponegoro Army was pinched. In 1829, Kyai Mojo, the spiritual leader of the rebellion, was arrested. Following that, Prince Mangkubumi and his chief commander, Alibasah Sentot Prawirodirjo, surrendered to the Dutch. Finally, on March 28, 1830, General De Kock succeeded in pinning Diponegoro's troops in Magelang. There, Pangeran Diponegoro stated that he was willing to surrender on the condition that the remaining members of his army were released. Therefore, Pangeran Diponegoro was arrested and exiled to Manado, then transferred to Makassar until his death in Fort Rotterdam on January 8, 1855.

Figure 6. Battle at Pluntaran.

Because for some people in the Yogyakarta Palace, Diponegoro was considered a rebel. Diponegoro's descendants were no longer allowed to enter the palace until Sri Sultan Hamengkubuwono IX gave amnesty to Diponegoro's descendants by considering the national spirit possessed by Diponegoro at that time. Now Diponegoro's children and grandchildren can freely enter the palace, especially to take care of their genealogy, without fear of being expelled.

III. THE END OF THE WAR

3. The end of the war

On the other hand, the Netherlands was facing the Padri War in West Sumatra. The cause of the Paderi War was a dispute between the Padri (alim ulama) and the Indigenous People (indigenous people). They questioned the Islamic religion, religious teachings, drunkenness, gambling, maternalism, and paternalism. This is when the Dutch stepped in and tried to take a chance. In the end, however, the Dutch had to fight both the adat and the clergy who had recently united. The Paderi War took place in two stages: round I between 1821-1825 and round II.

To face the Diponegoro War, the Dutch were forced to withdraw troops used in West Sumatra to meet Prince Diponegoro, a persistent guerrilla. A truce was agreed upon in 1825, and most of the soldiers from West Sumatra were diverted to Java. However, after the Diponegoro War ended (1830), the paper of the ceasefire

agreement was torn, and the second round of the Padri War occurred. In 1837 the leader of the Paderi War, Tuanku Imam Bonjol, was finally arrested. End the Padri War.

After the Diponegoro war, in 1832, all kings and regents in Java submitted to surrender to the Dutch except for the regent of Ponorogo Warok Brotodiningrat III. Instead, they wanted to attack all Dutch offices in the cities of Madiun and Central Java, such as Wonogori, the most inhabited Karanganyar. By Warok.

In Dutch records, the Waroks, who had battle skills and immunity, was very strong for Dutch troops. Therefore, to avoid detrimental to the Dutch, an agreement was made to create a Regent's office in the center of Ponorogo City, as well as supporting facilities such as paved roads, railroads, direct vehicles from Europe such as cars, motorbikes, and wind bikes of various brands, so no. surprised until now the city with the most significant number of old bicycles was in Ponorogo which at that time was used by the Waroks as well.

4. Another story about the Java War

There are many exciting stories about this Javanese war that can be taken as lessons. It needs further research because it sometimes seems controversial. Among others:

a. Fort Stelsel

Fort Stelsel or Fortress Rules is a war strategy adopted by the Dutch to defeat its enemies. General de Kock initiated this war tactic, then applied it to the Diponegoro War, and for the Dutch victory in the war, this strategy was again used in the Padri War.

Broadly speaking, the strategy of this war was that in every area that had been successfully controlled by the Dutch, a fortress or fort was built, then connecting infrastructure such as roads or bridges was built from each of these strongholds.

The use of the Fort Stelsel strategy, on the one hand, succeeded in accelerating costly warfare by pinning the enemy's position while controlling the territory under control, but on the other hand, this tactic had an impact on the deployment of a lot of forced labor, especially to build infrastructure to support this strategy (Benteng Stelsel - Google Arts & Culture, nd)(*Benteng Stelsel — Google Arts & Culture*, n.d.).

On the other hand, the western part outside the Yogyakarta region also experienced an expansion in the Bagelen, Magelang, and other Kedu residency areas. The influence of Diponegoro's resistance is increasingly widespread. This development carried out by Diponegoro made the Dutch confused about overcoming it. To deal with the attacks of Diponegoro troops moving from one post to another, General de Kock then implemented a strategy with the 'Benteng Stelsel' system (History of the Dutch "Fort Stelsel" Strategy in the Diponegoro War | Merdeka.Com, n.d.-b)(*Sejarah Strategi "Benteng Stelsel" Belanda Di Perang Diponegoro | Merdeka.Com*, n.d.-b).

b. The Life Story of Singadwipa, the Last Knight in the Java War from Banyumas

The Java War, 1825-1830 AD, or the war of Pangeran Diponegoro, almost eliminated the VOC and the Dutch colonial government. This is the most significant and most protracted war in the history of the fight for independence in Indonesia.

It turns out that the Java War did not last just six years. History records that the Java war ended when Prince Diponegoro was arrested and exiled to Sulawesi. However, the Java War was still going on even though the scale was not as big as before Prince Diponegoro was captured. Is Grandma Kiai Ngabehi Singadipa, one of the warlords who continued the Java War.

However, because the strength of the troops was not as immense as when Prince Diponegoro was still in charge, guerrilla was the strategy of choice. Kiai Singadipa is a warlord for troops in the western sector, the Banyumas Raya area. He understands every region in this area. The process was quite inconvenient for the Dutch, who never caught this slippery commander.

Its strategy in the Javanese war is well known to this day, namely 'Umpetan jeroning kemben,' or is interpreted as taking refuge behind a kemben cloth. Kemben is a cloth worn by Javanese women at that time. Chairman of the Singadipa Family Association, Bing Urip Hartoyo, said historians stated that the

commander disguised himself as an ordinary citizen during the guerrilla war. To perfect his disguise, he took a wife from the village where he lived to strategize in the Javanese war.

Figure 7. Java war. © Indonesia.go.id

The Java War in 1825-1830 was one of the biggest wars during the struggle for power from the Dutch colonialists. Not only Prince Diponegoro, this battle also gave birth to many heroes scattered in various areas of the battlefield.

After fighting it out for five years, this war had to end when Prince Diponegoro was captured and exiled by the Dutch to Sulawesi. But in fact, this war did not stop completely. In remote villages, the struggle continues. One of the figures who appeared at that time was Eyang Kiai Ngabehi Singadwipa (Life Story of Singadwipa, The Last Knight of the Javanese War from Banyumas | Merdeka.Com, n.d.)(*Kisah Hidup Singadwipa, Ksatria Terakhir Perang Jawa Asal Banyumas Halaman 3 | Merdeka.Com, n.d.*).

Kiai Singadwipa is one of the commanders of the Java War who fought in the Banyumas Raya area. Known as a figure who never gave up, Kiai Singadwipa turned out to have a unique war strategy. What is that strategy? The following is complete:

1) The Forgotten Hero

Figure 8. Diponegoro arrests © Wikipedia.org
Kiai Singadwipa can be said to be a forgotten hero.

Chairman of the Singadwipa Family Association, Bing Urip Hartoyo, said there was an attempt to erase the historical narrative of the Javanese War by the Dutch government. The Dutch government acknowledged that the Java War only lasted from 1825-1830, and ended when Prince Diponegoro was captured (The Life of Singadwipa, The Last Knight of the Javanese War from Banyumas Page 2 | Merdeka.Com, n.d.)(*Kisah Hidup Singadwipa, Ksatria Terakhir Perang Jawa Asal Banyumas Halaman 3 | Merdeka.Com, n.d.*).

Before being arrested, Pangeran Diponegoro had given a direct mandate to Kiai Singadwipa to continue the struggle in the Kertek area, Wonosobo. Kiai Singadwipa answered that order with ten years of guerrilla warfare. During that time, he was never caught. "Until 1830, when Prince Diponegoro was arrested, the Dutch never entered Banyumas Raya. They only reach Kertek, Wonosobo," said Bing Urip.

2) Have a Unique War Strategy

Figure 9. Java War © Wikipedia.org

One thing that Kiai Singadwipa still remembers is his unique war strategy. The war strategy was called "Umpetan jeroning kemben," or taking cover behind a kemben cloth.

The phrase implies that Kiai Singadwipa disguised himself as an ordinary citizen and married women in every place he stopped during the guerrilla war. So no wonder he has many wives. Kiai Singadwipa did this so that his descendants were many. With many descendants, it is hoped that their children and grandchildren can continue their struggle in the future (Life Story of Singadwipa, The Last Knight of the Java War from Banyumas Page 3 | Merdeka.Com, n.d.)(*Kisah Hidup Singadwipa, Ksatria Terakhir Perang Jawa Asal Banyumas Halaman 3 | Merdeka.Com, n.d.*).

Some of his well-known descendants are Suparjo Rustam and Susilo Sudarman. Suparjo is the guardian of the Commander in Chief, General Soedirman, who also served as the Governor of Central Java. Meanwhile, Susilo was a military figure who had served as a minister. Now, Achmad Husein, who is also a descendant of Singadwipa, is the Regent of Banyumas.

3) Deserves to be awarded the title of National Hero

Figure 10. Javanese war © Indonesia.go.id

During his guerrilla warfare, Kiai Singadwipa was never caught by the Dutch. Even when he died, his figure was so respected and recognized by both his children and grandchildren and the general public (Life Story of Singadwipa, The Last Knight of the Javanese War from Banyumas Page 4 | Merdeka.Com, n.d.)(*Kisah Hidup Singadwipa, Ksatria Terakhir Perang Jawa Asal Banyumas Halaman 2 | Merdeka.Com, n.d.*).

In fact, President Soeharto made two pilgrimages to the commander's grave. That is why the Singadwipa Family Association (IKS) wants their ancestors to be awarded National Heroes.

c. A Series of Corrupt Practices that Started the Javanese War of Pangeran Diponegoro

Figure 11. Raden Saleh / Painting Collection of the Presidential Palace

Raden Saleh's masterpiece painting tells the story of the atmosphere of Prince Diponegoro's arrest.

After the fall of the VOC to the Dutch colonialists who were under French influence, the Dutch East Indies made a change in administration through Governor-General Herman Willem Daendels. But the practice of corruption was still rampant not only by the colonial government but also by the Mataram Sultanate, which made Pangeran Diponegoro stifled (Series of Corrupt Practices as a Prayer for the

Javanese War of Pangeran Diponegoro - National Geographic, n.d.)(*Rentetan Praktik Korupsi Pemantik Perang Jawa Pangeran Dipanagara - National Geographic, n.d.*).

A few years ago, Peter Carey conveyed, "The practice of corruption is not new in the way of life of society but has existed for a long time through a seminar held by the Corruption Eradication Commission. Corruption is considered capable of destroying the social order and can even trigger political-economic instability. It is suspected that the Diponegoro war one of the causes was the corrupt practices that were rampant at that time".

Onghokham, also in Tradition and Corruption, added that in the scope of the Sultanate in Java, the definition of state money was the King's money. At that time, buying and selling positions was considered legal by paying tribute to the King.

"In Mataram, there is no center that manages state finances, or there is no centralization of finance. Each position is independent and autonomous; one has nothing to do with the other," he wrote. "Here, there is no separation between private and public interests."

Through his book entitled Takdir: The History of Pangeran Diponegoro, corruption also triggers the Java War. He wrote that Prince Diponegoro had slapped Patih Danureja IV of Yogyakarta with a slipper due to leasing royal land given to Europeans.

It is undeniable that leasing land to Europeans brought lucrative profits that corrupted the sultanate officials. The rental is obtained through the practice of bribery which can inflate the pockets of officials.

In Orang Cina, Bandar Tol, Opium, and the Java War, Carey said that in the transaction of plantation products, there were many facilitation payments in the customs of city gate guards. A city gate is commonplace in extortion and confiscation of native garden products, so the facilitation payments function so that complaints do not reach the ears of Javanese officials.

Figure 12. François Vincent Henri Antoine de Stuers / KITLV
Painting of when Diponegoro and his 800 troops set up camp in a delta on the Progo River. The island is located in Meteseh Hamlet, Magelang City, not far from Kedu Resident House.

"Besides, the twists and turns of procedures for bringing cases to court or before the authorities are ways that are beyond the capabilities of the average farmer," Carey wrote. "The only way that can be

taken, to be able to take his revenge seriously, is to ask the help of local experts to loot the toll gate (enter the city) or burn it."

But again, these efforts at anarchism were in vain because the government would retaliate with Javanese legislation, causing even higher losses of life. Long before the Java war, Governor-General Daendels only gave anti-corruption measures to colonial officials and allowed this practice to happen to the natives.

Daendels' policy, which can be considered the beginning of forming the rule of law (*rechtsaat*), also caused regents who were usually held by private groups to lose their income. Especially in the teak trade monopoly sector, which fell into the hands of Chinese entrepreneurs.

Carey considered this practice to be a trigger for anti-Chinese sentiment in the approaching Java War, in addition to the Prince Diponegoro scandal with Chinese Peranakan masseuses and city gatekeepers who were generally filled with Chinese descent.

The complexity of the problem of illicit actions got worse, especially when Governor-General van der Capellent issued a decree on May 6, 1823, for the land to be returned to the owner. The Yogyakarta Palace is threatened with bankruptcy; the law also obliges landowners to compensate for the deadline for returning land by European tenants.

This policy made Diponegoro even more disappointed with the Sultanate. Because, instead of stopping illicit practices, the Sultanate allowed and sided with the Dutch. As a result of this abuse and injustice towards the community, he cut ties with the Sultanate (Series of Corruption Practices of the Princes of Diponegoro Javanese War - Page 2 - National Geographic, n.d.)(*Retnetan Praktik Korupsi Pemantik Perang Jawa Pangeran Dipanagara - Halaman 2 - National Geographic, n.d.*).

d. Sinophobia

The Chinese community that was seen as an ally by Raden Ronggo in his rebellion turned into an enemy in the Diponegoro war. This is due to the emergence of anti-Chinese attitudes by the Javanese people, which are caused by the following:

- 1) The economic policies that were burdensome to the people by the Yogyakarta Palace due to Dutch government intervention were carried out through the mediation of ethnic Chinese.
- 2) The teak trade monopoly imposed by Daendels (1809) caused the local regents to lose their income which fell to Chinese entrepreneurs.
- 3) The Kapitan Tionghoa in Yogyakarta, Tan Jin Sing, during the invasion of British troops, sepoys, and Notokusumo's troops to the Yogyakarta Palace (June 1812).
- 4) Raffles' tax policy (1812-1813) for peasants to pay land tax in cash and eliminate corpse labor was not on target because Javanese farmers were accustomed to bartering. As a result, they fell into debt to local Chinese moneylenders who were given the authority to pay taxes.
- 5) The excise gate (Bandar) monopoly policy by the Dutch (1816) caused the fiscal costs to be incurred by Chinese entrepreneurs to increase sharply and impact the Javanese farmers they employed.
- 6) The prohibition of Pangeran Diponegoro from establishing political relations with ethnic Chinese according to the warning of his ancestor, Sultan Mangkubumi.
- 7) Prince Diponegoro's assumption written in his Babad that he was seduced by an ethnic Chinese masseuse on the night before the Gawok war (October 1828), causing him to lose his immunity (received wounds during the war) and suffered defeat.
- 8) The defeat of Tumenggung Sosrodilogo, the regent of Bojonegoro and the Prince's brother-in-law, was considered Diponegoro in January 1828 Sosrodilogo had touched a Peranakan Chinese in Lasem.

Attacks against ethnic Chinese in Central and East Java occurred since the beginning of the war. Note Payen, an architect in Yogyakarta, states that the Chinese community in Yogyakarta was massacred without caring for women or children. The Chinese community in Bagelen lasted until 1827 before being evacuated to Wonosobo. However, the Chinese community on the north coast (around Tuban and Lasem) also supplied Diponegoro's troops with weapons, money, and opium (at that time, many Javanese were

addicted opium, including Diponegoro's troops). After the war ended, the harmony between the Chinese community and other communities in Java could not return to normal because of mutual suspicion due to trauma during the war, for example, the incident in Bagelen when local Javanese people asked the displaced Chinese community to return.

IV. FOURTEEN HIDDEN FACTS BEHIND THE FEROCITY OF THE JAVANESE WAR

5. Fourteen hidden facts behind the ferocity of the Javanese war

Figure 13. KITLV

Lithography is based on a sketch of Francois Vincent Henri Antoine ridder de Stuers, a major-aide and son-in-law of Lieutenant-General Hendrik Merkus de Kock. Tells about the atmosphere when Diponegoro arrived at his emergency guesthouse in Metesih, on the banks of Kali Progo, Magelang, on March 8, 1830.

"The Java War had been prepared for 12 years," said Saleh As'ad Djamhari, a historian and military observer. "Diponegoro has carried out a conspiracy in silence with patience, secrecy, and secrecy." The Prince formed a *bekel*, *demang*, regents, *ulama*, *santri*, and farmers to build strength. With support funds from the aristocrats and the seizure of a Dutch logistical convoy, he set up a gunpowder factory on the outskirts of Yogyakarta. He bought a bolt-fired gun — presumably Prussian.

Peter Brian Ramsay Carey, one of the most famous historians from Great Britain, said that the early years of the war were indeed full of terror against the Chinese. Laskar Diponegoro was calling for hatred against the Chinese people, even slaughtering at first," said Carey. "That Chinese people are needed to become providers because they have networks on the coast. They smuggled gunpowder in packages of salted fish"—some were fighting on Diponegoro's side!

The Javanese War became a great history for its significant costs and casualties and the political-military aspects that surrounded it: the problem of sovereignty, Diponegoro's desire to form an Islamic state and the modern military organization used by the two opposing sides.

Figure 14. KITLV

Map of the invasion of Pleret on June 9, 1826, by Dutch troops and auxiliaries of native origin.

This was a five-year war (July 20, 1825, to March 28, 1830) that made the Dutch almost destroy and obliterate the Yogyakarta Palace. Consider the following eleven facts - which people may have forgotten - behind the fierce rage of the Java War:

a. Diponegoro is not a person's name

"Diponegoro" is a noble title used in the south-central Javanese palace. Before the Javanese War instigator named Diponegoro, it was recorded that two people used this title. Ratu Bendana, a daughter of Sultan Mangkubumi, was once married to a Surakarta aristocrat named Pangeran Diponegoro. This Prince died in 1787 and was buried in Kuncen, Yogyakarta. Much earlier, in the early 18th century, one of Pakubuwana I's sons also rebelled during the Second Javanese War of Succession. The name of the rebellious aristocrat is Diponegoro, and in Babad, Tanah Jawi takes the title "Erucakra" as well. He reportedly "disappeared" in Lumajang in 1723.

However, after the Java War, the title Diponegoro was no longer used in court circles, either Yogyakarta or Surakarta. It seems that Diponegoro is an unlucky name.

b. Almost Killed on Her Birthday

This is an unlucky gift for the Prince, right on his 44th birthday. Andreas Victor Michiels almost captured Diponegoro while fleeing in the Gowong Mountains, west of Kedu, on November 11, 1829. Dutch soldiers and Arafura gave chase under Michiels' command. However, the Prince managed to jump over the cliff and hide in the grove of reeds. If Diponegoro had died in the pursuit, the story of the

Javanese War would not have been as heroic as this — we would never have come across the story of the chronicle.

Figure 15. KITLV

Prince Diponegoro (1785-1855)

c. The Compact Diponegoro Laskar

Opium is widely used as a stimulant and part of Javanese medicine to cure various diseases. When the anti-Chinese feeling of the early months of the war eased a little, the Chinese had the advantage of being opium hookers on the back. During the Java War, there were reports that many Diponegoro soldiers fell ill due to addiction to madat. Reported by Captain Raden Mas Suwangsa, a cavalry officer of the Mangkunagaran Legion, captured by the Diponegoro army and brought to Selarong Village at the beginning of the Java War. He said, "The princes used to sleep until nine or ten in the morning, and some of them became madat slaves."

d. The Feminine Side of the Prince

During the war, he did not have the heart to take up arms. Towards the dead victims lying on both sides, he felt sorrowful; in fact, he even closed his eyes. Diponegoro revealed this to Second Lieutenant Julius Heinrich Knoerle, a German officer escorting him on his voyage to Manado. It could be that this psychological side is influenced by many women who have raised and raised him.

Figure 16. Mahandis Y. Thamrin / National Geographic Indonesia

Ki Roni Sodewo, a descendant of the seventh Prince Diponegoro from a child named Raden Mas Alip or Ki Sadewa, cleaned the abandoned tomb belonging to Captain Hermanus Volkers van Ingen. The Diponegoro army killed the captain and his beloved Irish-red-setter. The two were buried together.

e. The Tomb of the Captain and His Beloved Dog

On the eve of the 1829 New Year's celebrations in Nanggulan, a wild chase operation had brought destruction to a skeleton of East Indies soldiers. In this unbalanced battle, Captain Hermanus Volkers van Ingen and his beloved Irish-red-setter were killed at the hands of Laskar Diponegoro. Now, the graves of the two are still found in Nanggulan, west of the Progo River. The inscription that explains the two is hard to read, so the local people think that the grave beside the captain is his horse.

f. Fortress Stelsel System

Since May 1827, the Dutch implemented the newest tactic in their combat history: Constructing an emergency battlefield fort to clamp Diponegoro's movements. The fort used abundant local resources, such as coconut and bamboo trees. Dynamic nature, following the siege motion. During 1825-1829, 258 forts were built — the densely populated areas were in Mataram. In this strategy, eight fast-moving troops based on the site were arranged; towards the end of the war, it was fourteen. The architect of the fort was Colonel Frans David Cochius. After the war, his name was immortalized as an octagonal fort in Gombong, Central Java.

Figure 17. Raden Saleh / Painting Collection Presidential Palace

Raden Saleh's masterpiece painting which tells the story of the atmosphere of Prince Diponegoro's arrest.

g. Turkish versus Dutch Military Organization

Laskar Diponegoro, with Turkish-USmani-style organizations: Bulkiya, Barjumuah, Turkiya, Harkiya, Larban, Nasseran, Pinilih, Surapadah, Sipuding, Jagir, Suratandang, Jayengan, Suryagama, and Wanang Prang. The hierarchy of rank also has a Turkish accent: Ali Basah equal to the division commander wet equivalent to the brigade commander, Abdullah similar to the battalion commander, and is set equal to the company commander. The first time in the Javanese military ranks was known. Like Diponegoro, his soldiers were also in turbans and had their heads shaved off — bald.

East Indies soldiers, with European-style organizations. The East Indies soldiers were not native Dutch. The regular army — infantry, cavalry, artillery, and pioneers — consisted of Europeans and natives. They were strengthened by the Hulptroepen, a unit of indigenous soldiers from the Mangkunagara Legion, the Mangkudiningrat line, the Natapraja line, Sumenep, Madura, Pamekasan, Bali, Manado, Gorontalo, Buton, and the Maluku Islands. Then, Jayeng Sekar, horse-riding police recruited from each residency. Others: mirrors, Islamic clergy, coolies, servants, cooks, and washermen.

Figure 18. Rijksmuseum

Portrait of Hendrik Merkus Baron de Kock, after 1826, served as lieutenant governor-general of the Dutch East Indies. Painting by Cornelis Kruseman, circa 1826-1845.

h. The honesty of the General

After Diponegoro was framed at the Resident's guesthouse in Magelang, De Kock admitted his cunning in his diary. "I fully understand; my actions like that are not praiseworthy, not knightly and cunning because Diponegoro has come to Magelang with my faith and honesty to hold negotiations with me. After all, he could not have had any evil plans "Then De Kock continued," If I caught Diponegoro, then that would undoubtedly make an unfavorable impression. "

i. The fate of the Diponegoro House

After the war, Diponegoro's descendants in exile outside Java were still encouraged by the Dutch to use the title of Prince. The goal is to make it easier to supervise. Meanwhile, Diponegoro's descendants who were in Java were continuously searched for and removed from relatives in the palace - until they were killed. They chose to inhabit the slopes of the mountains around Yogyakarta. A great-grandson of Diponegoro once founded the Diponegoro Education Court in 1954 in Yogyakarta. The goal is that the Diponegoro people in remote areas of Gunung Kidul and Bagelen can get scholarships to study in Yogyakarta. Despite the availability of money and support, no one was willing to claim Diponegoro's descent.

j. The Javanese War seems to have been predicted by the Dutch

The Dutch government received revenue from toll booths run by Chinese who had just arrived from Fujian. A few years before the Java War, toll gate ports were increasingly troubling the people. They collect taxes blindly and are often disrespectful when searching for women. Then, the Resident of Surakarta and the Resident of Yogyakarta formed a kind of audit team that uncovered the actions of toll gates. This audit team proposed to the governor-general to remove the toll gates in the two kingdoms.

"That if the toll gates are still allowed to continue their activities, then the time will not be long before the Javanese will rise terribly."

Figure 19. Mahandis Y. Thamrin / National Geographic Indonesia

Wayang Diponegoro by Ledjar Subroto, which was staged at the Jakarta National Gallery, June 2012.

Onghokham, a historian and scholar, once said that it was rare for kings in the archipelago who did not hesitate to collect people's help for military-political power. "Hamengkubuwana, Diponegoro, and I are exceptions," he said. However, several cases in Southeast Asia show that "popular or peasant insurrection does not change the structure of society."

"The permanent structure always consists of the royal elite and the priyayi, and on the other hand are the common people," said Onghokham. "They are still little people."

k. Handover of the Prince Diponegoro War Flag

Figure 20. Haul and pilgrimage to the grave of Eyang Kiai Singadipa, the warlord of Pangeran Diponegoro in the Java war. (Liputan6.com/Angga/Muhamad Ridlo)

Because they had to move around to avoid sniffing Dutch intelligence, Singadipa ended up marrying six women. Other sources even record Singadipa's wife more than that. "To marry six women until the end of their lives," he said, Saturday night (11/9/2019). Bing said there was an attempt to dwarf

the history of the Javanese war and the story of the heroism of Kiai Singadipa by the Dutch government. The Dutch government only acknowledged that the Java war took place between 1825- 1830, or just five to six years.

They are worried that the figure of Kiai Singadipa will become a spirit of rebellion. Because of this, his heroic figure and story were eliminated (The Story of Kiai Singadipa, The Last Knight in the Java War - Regional Liputan6.Com, n.d.)(*Kisah Kiai Singadipa, Ksatria Terakhir Perang Jawa - Regional Liputan6.Com, n.d.*).

"Until 1830, when Prince Diponegoro was arrested, the Dutch could never enter Banyumas Raya. They only reach Kertek, Wonosobo," said Bing.

Also, in Kertek, the commander received a mandate directly from Prince Diponegoro. Just before Prince Diponegoro was arrested sneakily, Prince Diponegoro's war flag or war pataka, Kiai Tunggul Wulung, was handed over to Singadipa.

The command to continue this struggle was answered by Kiai Singadipa with evidence of 10 years of guerrilla warfare. During that time, Singadipa was never caught. Once served as Wedana Ajibarang, Kiai Singadipa died and was buried in Panembangan, Cilongok, Banyumas. And now, his descendants are scattered throughout Banyumas, Indonesia, and even abroad.

1. Semarang Chinatown Anxiety When Facing Upbeat Diponegoro

Figure 21. Mahandis Yoanata Thamrin / NGI

Javanese war themed batik collection of the Dinar Hadi Museum, Surakarta. This war broke out on Wednesday, July 20, 1825. The beginning of this long and tiring war was marked by the attack and burning of Diponegoro's residence in Tegalrejo by joint Dutch-Keraton troops.

The Javanese War broke out in Yogyakarta in mid-1825. However, rumors spread to the north coast of Java. The news that was also reported varied: a king was in rebellion, an enemy from abroad who was at war with Dutch soldiers, to the action of rioters. In Semarang, the news worried the residents.

The politics of segregation has become a character of the Java War. The massacre of Chinatowns carried out by Diponegoro's troops was not a Garib thing at the beginning of the war. Since declaring himself as "Sultan Ngabdulkamid Erucakra Sayidin Panatagama Khalifat Rasulullah" in August 1825, Diponegoro called for destroying the Dutch and Chinese in Java if they were not willing to embrace Islam. It seems that at the beginning of this war, the Prince saw that the Chinese were the source of the Javanese economic oppression.

The massacre of Chinatowns carried out by Diponegoro's troops was not a Garib thing at the beginning of the war. It was only in the following months that the Semarang Chinatown residents learned of the actual events. Dutch soldiers often stopped in Semarang before they continued to crush the rebellion in Grobogan. Residents dubbed this period Geger Diponegoro.

About a century after the Java War, Liem Thian Joe (1895-1963) wrote about the restlessness of Semarang's Chinatowns when Diponegoro's army carried out the massacre of Chinese people. Liem is a seasoned journalist from Parakan but grew up in Semarang.

For the security of the Semarang Chinatown area, Liem said, the Chinese chief, Tan Tiang Tjhing, requested the Dutch government. Sang Kapitan's request to build a gate in the four corners of Chinatown was granted.

Figure 22. Hafidz Novalsyah / National Geographic Indonesia

Citizens of Chinese descent worship at Tay Kak Sie Temple, in the Chinatown area, Semarang.

One gate was built at the end of Jalan Sebandaran, on the road that bends towards Jagalan. Then another gate at the mouth of Jalan Cap-kauw-king (now Jalan Wotgandul Barat) Petak Sembilan area in Beteng. The gate at Gang Warung (now the main Chinatown door) around the west end of Lor's Chinatown. Then, the entrance is across from Pekojan Bridge (now Jalan Pekojan). Liem said that the four gates were built through funds collected from residents of Semarang's Chinatown.

Liem revealed that the four gates were covered with thick walls, so they were not easy to break. A large door is made in one entrance, and a small door is made in a large door. The gate is guarded by turns of the Chinatown residents who have grown up every night.

"The door is closed every day when the weather starts to get dark," said Liem, "only those who have essential needs are allowed to go out, and they have to go through the small door that was deliberately made in the door, just enough for one person to leave or enter. "

Liem revealed that the four gates were covered with thick walls, so they were not easy to break.

One of the sadistic massacres was carried out by Raden Ayu Yudakusuma, the daughter of the Second Sultan. He was the commander of the massacre of Chinese citizens in Ngawi in September 1826. At the end of the following year, Raden Tumenggung Aria Sasradilaga, Diponegoro's brother-in-law, massacred Chinatowns in Lasem and beat Chinese women force — rape.

It seems that news of the massacre in the north coast of Java reached the ears of the Chinese chief, Tan Tiang Tjhing. He had made a critical decision: If the citizens lost this battle, the Tay Kak Si Temple and the women and children who fled in it would be burned down so that they would not be persecuted. The Kapitan also made a defense in the form of a pile of firewood around the temple.

Figure 23. "The History of Semarang" —Liem Thian Joe

One of the gates of Semarang's Chinatown was built in four directions. This gate is thought to have been made at the beginning of the Java War. Now, this historic building has disappeared. Photo in the

book "History of Semarang" by Liem Thian Joe, which was first published by Boekhandel Ho Kim Joe-Semarang-Batavia in 1933. In 2004, Publisher Hasta Wahana Jakarta published again.

Liem recounts that one day in 1826, the Chinatowns immediately closed their shops and prepared to face the resistance of the "hoodlums" —that is, Liem said, the gang of vandals who often attack Chinatowns. Strength is concentrated at the gate of Pekojan because they think that the "thugs" who attack Chinatown must pass through the gate.

"People have chosen the great pagoda as a place of sacrifice," said Liem, "there is no place more holy than the pagoda [...] so that if they are burned there, their spirits will be protected."

This unrest hit the Semarang Chinatown and their neighbors: the residents of Pekojan - a Muslim village of Koja descent from Gujarat, West India. Liem said that the two villages worked together to dispel the intruders who often massacred the Chinese in the early years of the Java War. It seems that differences in beliefs do not prevent them from setting an example of neighborliness.

They moved to Gedangan, the eastern side of the city. The Koja was in the front row, while the Chinese were in the back. "If they run into hoodlums," said Liem, "the Koja group will signal with one big firecracker eruption, and the Chinese group must come to help."

It seems that their differences in beliefs do not prevent them from setting an example of living next door. Initially, the story about the social and cultural life of the Chinese people in Semarang was revealed by Liem in a series of notes published in the Central Java Review magazine from March 1931 to July 1933. Furthermore, in the second half of 1933, Liem's writings in the magazine were put together in *Riwajat Semarang's* book. : From Sam Poo's past to his appreciation of Kongkoan. Then, about a decade ago, the book was republished.

Although it seems that Semarang's Chinatown survived the looting and massacres, the incidents of the Java War had become a landmark for residents. "Many Chinese children or indigenous people who were born at that time were given the name Geger," said Liem, "for a warning that the child was born during the chaos era."

History records that Tan Tiang Tjhing was appointed as the titular lieutenant in 1809 and became the first Chinese major in Semarang in 1829. A year before serving as major, the captaincy was passed on to his son, Tan Hong Yan. The names of this father and son are well-known because they also controlled the madat business in Java in the early 19th century.

Figure 24. Budi ND Dharmawan

An actor dances as Diponegoro in the dramatic reading of Babad Diponegoro.

The relationship between Java and China is like the ebb and flow of seawater in this country. Before the Java War, had their relationship always been in hatred?

I saw Carey again. This time we talked at his elegant residence, on the east bank of Cisadane River, South Tangerang. In his living room, he displays a portrait of Prince Diponegoro in a contemporary style.

In the late 18th century, Chinese descendants played various roles in Java: businessman for the court, medical expert, to a concubine. From the palace manuscripts seized by the British, Carey said that the Second Sultan had a personal healer of Chinese descent. He also had a concubine named Mas Ayu Sumarsanawati, who was of Chinese descent on the north coast. The concubine gave birth to Jayakusuma, Diponegoro's uncle, who became his commander and war tactician, he said.

"I think," said Carey, "when Diponegoro was raised in Yogya in the late 18th, and early 19th centuries, there had not been any apartheid between Chinese and Javanese." He suspected that Diponegoro's first wife was of Chinese descent. "What got terrible was after the Dutch returned. The Dutch enforced a system allied with Chinese descent as a toll road. "

Why did the Chinese want to join forces to blackmail in the 1820s? They were newcomers from Fujian who did not speak Javanese — let alone know the culture — and did not speak Malay fluently.

The beginning of the war was indeed full of terror against Chinese citizens. However, lately, the Javanese have missed them too. "The situation is like going back to the way it was," he said. "That Chinese people are needed to become providers because they have networks on the coast. They smuggled gunpowder in packages of salted fish"—some were fighting on Diponegoro's side!

Figure 25. Mahandis Y. Thamrin / National Geographic Indonesia
Wayang Diponegoro by Ledjar Subroto, which was staged at the Jakarta National Gallery, June 2012.

When hatred towards the Chinese was still roiling, Diponegoro and his troops spent the night in Kedaren, a cliff-fortified hamlet near Jatianom. In his chronicle, he recounts one night, a Chinese woman who was taken prisoner was sent as his masseuse. Then, the Prince was complacent and had an affair with the Chinese woman. According to Diponegoro, the night incident in Kedaren was what made him beaten in the battle of Gawok, October 1826. He was seriously injured in his left chest and right hand.

"He is not a hypocrite," said Carey. Diponegoro admits that her vices are still inherent, and she also admits that her weakness is towards women. "He's straightforward, and that's what's interesting about the chronicle."

Can we still find the four Chinatown gates built on the initiative of the Chinese Kapitan Tan Tiang Tjhing?

"Unfortunately, the four gates are no longer used," said Yogi Fajri, activist and head of the Lopen Semarang history community. According to his observations, many original buildings typical of Chinese architecture have disappeared and are hard to find on the main roads of the Chinatown area. "Most of it was overhauled during the New Order era," added Yogi, "and it continues today."

m. Diponegoro, Is It an Unlucky Name?

The Prince is incarnate as a controversial figure. Tragically, once upon a time, his name was not only worshiped as a hero but also hated as a rebel. How is the story of one citizen in Java? "Diponegoro is not a person's name," said Ki Roni Sodewo, a descendant of the seventh Prince Diponegoro who lives in Wates, Kulonprogo. "It is the title of prince used by the sons of kings in ancient times."

"Diponegoro" is a noble title used in the south-central Javanese palace. Before the Javanese War instigator named Diponegoro (1785-1855), it was recorded that two people used this title. Ratu Bendana, a daughter of Sultan Mangkubumi, was once married to a Surakarta aristocrat named Pangeran Diponegoro. This Prince died in 1787 and was buried in Kuncen, Yogyakarta. Much earlier, in the early 18th century, one of Pakubuwana I's sons also rebelled during the Second Javanese War of Succession. The name of the rebellious aristocrat is Diponegoro, and in Babad, Tanah Jawi takes the title "Erucakra" as well. He reportedly "disappeared" in Lumajang in 1723.

However, after the Java War, the title was no longer used by the Yogyakarta and Surakarta Palace. Diponegoro's descendants from a child named Raden Mas Alip - aka Ki Bagus Singlon or Ki Sadewa - have inhabited the area in Kulonprogo to the gorge of the Menoreh Mountains since the early 19th century. This Raden Mas Alip gave birth to the Diponegoron breed in Kulonprogo, including the Ki Roni family.

In 2007, Ki Roni founded the Prince Diponegoro Family Association (IKPD), which aims to unite the "separated bones" of the Prince's dynasty. The post-war terror of Java had made them hide their identity. Unlike the descendants of the Prince who were in Makassar and Ambon who were free to use the title of ancestral Prince, in Java, his descendants were chased down and killed - similar to the politics of exterminating the G30S perpetrators. No more royal family in southern Central Java dares to use his name. It seems to be the fact that Diponegoro is such an unlucky name.

"That was how painful the life of Diponegoro's descendants was at that time," said Ki Roni softly. "None of Diponegoro's grandchildren has left exile in Makassar or Ambon," he said, "because it is feared that they will still be able to gather strength." He revealed that the Diponegoro descendants who first left exile were Ahmad Diponegoro bin Abdullah Diponegoro from Ambon. Around the 1930s, he was

allowed to return to Java, said Ki Roni, because he was not allowed to be in East Java, Central Java, or even Yogyakarta. Finally, he lived in Cimahi, West Java as an employee of the Dutch East Indies railway company.

Diponegoro is a controversial figure. For the Dutch, he was a figure representing resistance to colonialism through the Sabil War. Meanwhile, on the Indonesian side, he was disliked by the Yogyakarta Palace because he was considered a traitor. The Diponegoro rebellion had made the Yogyakarta Palace almost exterminated by the Dutch.

"We only communicate via code," he said, remembering the tradition of Diponegoro descendants who were in Kulonprogo in establishing kinship. They used the family code by planting a yellow tree in their yard — a tree Diponegoro had also grown in his hermitage in Tegalrejo. He added that they usually also planted sapodilla trees to the right of the entrance. If the Javanese generally make a well on the left side of the house, they make it on the right side. One does not need to claim to be Diponegoro's descendants, he said, to look for someone of Diponegoro's descent; it is enough to see the signs earlier.

Figure 26. Mahandis Y. Thamrin / National Geographic Indonesia

Ki Roni Sodewo, the seventh descendant of Diponegoro, stands at the cemetery of his ancestral army in Dekso Village, Kulonprogo. There are at least 147 gravestones in the middle of the residents' garden. This village was once the Prince's headquarters in late 1825 - after the Dutch invaded Selarong - until 1826.

Times have changed, and the codes that Ki Roni described earlier have been abandoned by the current generation who have an open mind. After Sukarno commemorated the 100th anniversary of Diponegoro's death in Jakarta and Makassar in 1955, reconciliation began to reconcile between the Yogyakarta Palace and the Diponegoron dynasty. Even so, to this day in the hilly area of Menoreh, Ki Roni still finds Diponegoro descent families who uphold their ancestral message to keep their identities a secret. Joining the organization formed by Ki Roni, for them, means breaking their traditions.

To his relatives who still adhere to the ancestral message, Ki Roni once said, "Now the Dutch don't exist. This is the time for us to come together. It's time for us to show who we are; let's fight together because our struggle is not over for now. Our country is still like this, and it's not quite what the heroes want. And his wish is to live a prosperous life. "

n. The Yogyakarta Palace Is Involved in the Diponegoro Trapping Strategy?

Figure 27. Raden Saleh

Raden Saleh's masterpiece painting tells the story of the atmosphere of Prince Diponegoro's arrest.

Old and mysterious records from behind the walls of the Yogyakarta Palace reveal the final minutes of the humiliating Java War on March 28, 1830. Who made it? The Diponegoro rebellion ended the old place in Java. A long strand of new titimangsa stretched out: True colonialism in the Land of Java, a painful period with the whack of forced cultivation and the grinding of the wheels of private capital. Diponegoro lived a tragic life as an honorable prisoner of war. During this stay up to his last place of exile, he was never placed in prison. The Netherlands provides residential rooms in Fort Amsterdam in Manado and Fort Rotterdam in Makassar. The Yogyakarta Palace bore all costs of the Java War and Diponegoro's cost of living. He died in poverty on Monday, January 8, 1855, at the age of 69. Until the end of his life, the Prince still chose to be called Ngabdulkamid. His nemesis, Lieutenant General Hendrik Merkus de Kock, died ten years earlier.

Diponegoro is a controversial figure. For the Dutch, he was a figure who represented resistance to colonialism through the Sabil War. Meanwhile, for Indonesia, he is a figure that the Yogyakarta Palace does not like because he is considered a traitor. The Diponegoro rebellion had made the Yogyakarta Palace almost exterminated by the Dutch.

Figure 28. Mahandis Yoanata Thamrin / National Geographic Indonesia
The soldiers of the Ngayogyakarta Palace depart from the performance in the annual ceremony, Grebeg Maulud.

At the Yogyakarta Palace, I went to Kanjeng Raden Tumenggung Jatiningrat. He is the grandson of the Eighth Sultan, an elder who is polite and careful. We talked at his place of work as Pengageng Tepas Dwarapura. Jatiningrat read out a snippet of a Javanese manuscript, which had been kept tightly in the palace. He just dared to reveal the manuscript's contents to me because, according to him, the times had changed. As a result of his analysis of the manuscript, he suspects that the Yogyakarta Palace was involved in the Diponegoro trapping in Magelang.

"In the past, we admit that disputes led to one breed being sidelined. A good history is a history that can provide education for the successors of history. It's hard to speak the way it is, and often what it takes time. "

The manuscript tells that Raden Tumenggung Danokusuma II "suddenly" left the palace. He is, Diponegoro's brother-in-law. After Diponegoro had the title of Sultan Ngabdulkamid, Danokusuma II graduated as his governor, who had Raden Duke Abdullah Danureja.

After Diponegoro was lonely because of the abandonment of the warlords and his brothers, Abdullah took the initiative to consult De Kock, said Jatiningrat. Abdullah asked De Kock to hold peace at the Magelang Residency lodge immediately. On the appointed day, Diponegoro and De Kock were in the front room, while Abdullah came first in the back room. After Diponegoro was arrested, he went to face the Keraton again. Then, he had the title Kanjeng Adipati Danuningrat.

Figure 29. François Vincent Henri Antoine de Stuers / KITLV

Painting of when Diponegoro and his 800 troops set up camp in a delta on the Progo River. The island is located in Meteseh Hamlet, Magelang City, not far from Kedu Resident House.

Jatiningrat suspected that Abdullah was deliberately smuggled in a secret mission, not on the personal initiative because the proof was that he returned to the palace again. "This is a deliberation of the state, not individuals," he said. "This is something worth considering." "This is the palace's source that says that," said Jatiningrat. When I asked who the author was, with a smile, he refused to mention it. "In the past, we admit that disputes led to one breed being sidelined. A good history is a history that can provide education for the successors of that history, "he said. "It's hard to talk the way it is, and often what it takes time."

V. CLOSING

6. Conclusion.

We can take a precious lesson from the Java War, which took place almost two centuries ago. Among others:

- a. Leadership
- b. Passion
- c. Confidence
- d. Cooperation
- e. Willing to sacrifice
- f. Not concerned with one's interests
- g. Combat tactics and techniques

However, there are still many things that need more in-depth research. Many interesting stories have not been revealed and understood by the millennial generation.

7. Recommendation

It is necessary to carry out further research, especially on the unfavorable issues to Prince Diponegoro and his followers, so that there are no problems in the future

VI. Acknowledgments

"Friends, thank you for being a protector who is ready to prevent me from various kinds of dangers. Even you never bring up my horror in the past to anyone."

"To my wife as well as my heavenly angel. Thank you for accompanying me across the household ark together. Even though sometimes the storms hit, but you are still and always by my side."

"Sorry for all the anger that ever came out of me. Thank you for being patient with me."

"Thank you for all your dedication to me, thank you for all of your sacrifices while educating us. Thank you also for all your attention to us; you are the best teacher."

"My success in the work and the achievements that I have achieved cannot be separated from your support and guidance. Thank you for giving me a lot of inspiration to work well and with enthusiasm."

REFERENCES

- [1.] *Apa itu sistem benteng stelsel? Pengertian sistem benteng stelsel dan definisinya dalam Glosarium.* (n.d.). Retrieved February 22, 2021, from <https://glosarium.org/arti-sistem-benteng-stelsel/>
- [2.] *Apa Yang Dimaksud Dengan Benteng Stelsel Bagaimana Pelaksanaannya?* (n.d.). Retrieved February 22, 2021, from <https://www.plengdut.com/2019/10/pelaksanaannya-stelsel-benteng-apa-bagaimana-dimaksud-dengan-yang.html>
- [3.] *Apa yang Kamu Ketahui Tentang Perang Diponegoro? - Kelas Pintar.* (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2021, from <https://www.kelaspintar.id/blog/edutech/apa-yang-kamu-ketahui-tentang-perang-diponegoro-6590/>
- [4.] *Benteng Stelsel — Google Arts & Culture.* (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2021, from <https://artsandculture.google.com/entity/benteng-stelsel/g120mbs4r>
- [5.] *Kisah Hidup Singadwipa, Ksatria Terakhir Perang Jawa Asal Banyumas Halaman 2 | merdeka.com.* (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2021, from <https://www.merdeka.com/jateng/kisah-hidup-singadwipa-ksatria-terakhir-perang-jawa-asal-banyumas.html?page=2>
- [6.] *Kisah Hidup Singadwipa, Ksatria Terakhir Perang Jawa Asal Banyumas Halaman 3 | merdeka.com.* (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2021, from <https://www.merdeka.com/jateng/kisah-hidup-singadwipa-ksatria-terakhir-perang-jawa-asal-banyumas.html?page=3>
- [7.] *Kisah Kiai Singadipa, Ksatria Terakhir Perang Jawa - Regional Liputan6.com.* (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2021, from <https://www.liputan6.com/regional/read/4107079/kisah-kiai-singadipa-ksatria-terakhir-perang-jawa>
- [8.] *Perang Melawan Penjajahan Kolonial Belanda - Kelas Pintar.* (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2021, from <https://www.kelaspintar.id/blog/tips-pintar/perang-melawan-penjajahan-kolonial-belanda-8809/>
- [9.] *Rentetan Praktik Korupsi Pemantik Perang Jawa Pangeran Dipanagara - Halaman 2 - National Geographic.* (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2021, from <https://nationalgeographic.grid.id/read/132460804/rentetan-praktik-korupsi-pemantik-perang-jawa-pangeran-dipanagara?page=2>
- [10.] *Rentetan Praktik Korupsi Pemantik Perang Jawa Pangeran Dipanagara - National Geographic.* (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2021, from <https://nationalgeographic.grid.id/read/132460804/rentetan-praktik-korupsi-pemantik-perang-jawa-pangeran-dipanagara>
- [11.] *Sejarah strategi "Benteng Stelsel" Belanda di Perang Diponegoro | merdeka.com.* (n.d.-a). Retrieved

- April 20, 2021, from <https://www.merdeka.com/pendidikan/sejarah-strategi-benteng-stelsel-belanda-di-perang-diponegoro.html>
- [12.] *Sejarah strategi “Benteng Stelsel” Belanda di Perang Diponegoro* | *merdeka.com*. (n.d.-b). Retrieved February 22, 2021, from <https://www.merdeka.com/pendidikan/sejarah-strategi-benteng-stelsel-belanda-di-perang-diponegoro.html>
- [13.] *Tewasnya 15 ribu serdadu Belanda pada Perang Jawa*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 20, 2021, from <https://www.hops.id/perang-jawa/>